

ELIXIR Training Platform 2023 Face-to-Face Meeting Summary Report

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Background

ELIXIR stands as a collaborative intergovernmental entity, uniting a multitude of life science resources from across Europe. Its operational framework comprises five distinct areas, aptly referred to as Platforms: Compute, Data, Interoperability, Tools, and Training. As a testament to their commitment, each Platform annually convenes a pivotal conference known as the annual 'Face-to-Face/hybrid' Platform meeting. This gathering serves as an invaluable opportunity for disseminating updates, fostering insightful discussions, and collectively shaping strategies that steer the current and future undertakings of the Platform. The Training Platform held this year's annual meeting in early March 2023 in Rome, Italy.

Event format and participation

The ELIXIR Training Platform 2023 Face-to-Face meeting took place over 3 days at the Casa dell'Aviatore, Rome in a hybrid format. 25 members, Training Coordinators from Nodes and Training Specialists from across Europe travelled and attended in-person while 10 people were consistently participating remotely as the set up allowed for a hybrid experience. After a roundtable introduction of the participants and an icebreaker session, the meeting agenda was presented and the event kick-started.

Event content

The event commenced with a comprehensive overview of the Platform's progress over the past year, as Task leads shared updates and highlighted key developments. Additionally, they addressed the challenges that need to be resolved before the year's end, emphasising the importance of collaborative efforts in overcoming any existing obstacles.

One significant topic of discussion was TeSS, the Training E-support System, an ELIXIR Resource serving as a search portal for courses, events, videos, presentations, learning pathways, handbooks, including all types of resources at all levels for leveraging computational resources in the life sciences. The participants engaged in lively conversations about the system's sustainability, operational challenges, and strategies to enhance engagement and encourage contributions from Nodes. These discussions aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the training landscape and shape the future direction of TeSS.

A major highlight of the event was the presentation of the next ELIXIR Scientific Programme for 2024-2028 by our Chief Technical Officer, Peter Maccallum. This presentation offered valuable insights into funding estimates, strategic considerations, and the overall structure of future activities, providing a clear perspective on where the Training Platform fits within the broader ELIXIR framework.

The second day of the event was dedicated to shaping the Training Platform's activities in light of the new Programme. Training Platform members and Training Coordinators came together to

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brainstorm ideas, align their efforts, and identify areas where the Training Platform could make a significant impact and contribution. This collaborative session aimed to refine the Platform's objectives and outline a strategic roadmap for the future.

The final day of the event was devoted to reflection, allowing participants to critically evaluate their work, identify missed opportunities, and learn from both successful and unsuccessful endeavours. This self-assessment exercise provided valuable insights and lessons that will inform future initiatives and ensure continuous improvement within the Training Platform.

Overall, the event served as a space for fruitful discussions, strategic planning, and reflection on past achievements and challenges. The active engagement of participants fostered a collaborative environment, enabling the Training Platform and its members to chart its course for the future, align with the organisation's vision, and ultimately contribute to the advancement of life sciences training across Europe.

Significant event outcomes

The event was successful in fostering new connections and collaborations, concrete outcomes are as follows:

- Strategic priorities for the upcoming activities of the Training Platform as part of the 2024-2028 Scientific ELIXIR Programme.
- Set up the goals to reach by 2028:
 - Promoting standards and best practices for Open science and Open education, aligning to EOSC Initiatives and other global initiatives
 - Establishing a coherent federated Training Platform infrastructure, by seamlessly integrating existing technical services and resources
 - Building training capacity and skills within data life cycle topics coupled to bioinformatics and life sciences
 - Enabling the "ELIXIR Training Platform member" identity, that can support open, robust and ethical data-driven research in the life sciences
- Ongoing mapping of current efforts outside of ELIXIR (e.g., from Australian BioCommons, GOBLET) and plans to stay aligned in order to create a truly federated and synced training ecosystem.
- Outline the Work Packages and Tasks and open them for feedback to the wider community
- Developing a proposal for BioHackathon Europe 2023 participation.

Conclusion

In summary, the Face-to-Face/hybrid event organised by the ELIXIR Training Platform, supported by Italian Node representatives - thanks to who we were able to have a great time and real italian experience, was a resounding success, providing a rewarding experience for all attendees throughout the course of the event. The objective of reuniting Training Platform members and revitalising personal connections, given the absence of in-person gatherings in recent times, was effectively accomplished.

The feedback received from participants was overwhelmingly positive, reflecting the overall

satisfaction and engagement with the event. Valuable insights and suggestions provided by attendees have been carefully considered for future planning, ensuring continuous improvement and an enhanced experience for upcoming Training Platform events. The connections forged, the insights gained, and the positive energy generated during the event have set the stage for a promising future, full of growth, collaboration, and continued success for the Training Platform's activities.